

CHILDREN'S AND YOUTH'S PERSPECTIVES CONFERENCE:
THEORY, RESEARCH AND PRACTICE IN EUROPEAN CONTEXT
PRAGUE 14TH - 15TH SEPTEMBER 2023

CALL FOR ABSTRACTS

A critique of the adult-centred theory and research methods traditionally used in the exploration of children and adolescent's development and lives entered the discourse of social sciences in the 1990s with the theory of New Sociology of Childhood (James and Prout, 1997), arguing that children and young people are in traditional discourses considered by adults as incompetent in their skills before developing into fully respectable adults. In terms of research, children and youth are traditionally treated as research subjects who provide the data in adult-centred categories on children's themes, resulting in information about children that is directed, analysed, and produced by adults in adult-centred views. In addition, the discussion of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child has ignited the discussion on the implementation of children's rights in children's daily encounters with social institutions, such as family, education and schools, social services, health services, law institutes etc.

The child-centred perspective aims to acknowledge, address and empower children's voice and active agency considering children as active social agents with their experiences and perspectives that are relevant to society. Yet, traditional discourses and related social policies on children and childhood still present barriers to child-centred perspective, inclusion, and active participation of children in democratic institutions and societies.

This recent development in social sciences is embedded in the new discipline of Childhood (Children's) studies with an interdisciplinary approach to the child, children, and childhood. With a child-centred focus, new research methods are friendly to children's mode of communication, allowing active participation in research and thus more authentic exploration of children's experiences and perspectives of the lived social phenomena in question.

To contribute to the current discussion on a child-centred perspective and further development of Childhood/Children's studies in the EU and the Czech context, we invite, academics, researchers, PhD. candidates, and practitioners to present the research and theoretical/conceptual papers, posters, symposium of the 3-5 papers, and reflections on child-centred evidence-based practice in social institutions, on the following topics:

1. The child-and-youth-centred approach, in theory, policy, research and applied evidence-based practice in the EU and the Czech context
2. Interdisciplinarity and latest development in child-centred perspective and discipline of Childhood/Children's studies
3. Concepts of child's agency, power, empowerment, autonomy, participation and children's voice in the theory of Childhood/Children's studies
4. UN CRC and Children's rights in theory, research, policy, current debate and evidence-based practice in the EU and the Czech context
5. Arts-based and participatory child-centred research methodologies and methods and application in exploration of children's experiences, perceptions, rights and child-centred evidence based evaluation and practice
6. Arts-based and participatory child-centred research with rural children, youth and young adults (up to 25 years) in EU context
7. Arts-based and participatory child-centred research with urban children, youth and young adults (up to 25 years) in EU context
8. Youth mentoring and the perspective of Childhood/Children's studies in the EU context

Register with conference ABSTRACTS (350 words) [HERE](#) until 31st March 2023

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

Book of abstracts will be generated and distributed to all conference participants. Selected abstracts and presentations will be called as conference proceedings for Special Issue on the conference themes, details TBC.

CONFERENCE FEES

Conference participant
Conference participant with presentation
PhD. students

130 Euro / 3000 CZK
150 Euro / 3500 CZK
100 Euro / 2500 CZK

Session fees: Please, email us with request for details.

CONTACT DETAILS

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Children are considered here according to UN CRC as human beings between 0 - 18 years of age. Thus, the term 'children' includes children of 0 - 11 and young people in the age between 12 - 18 years in this conference synopsis. Young adults are people between 18 - 25 years of age also relevant for the conference call.